

Research Article

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On the oscillation of nonlinear delay differential equations and their applications

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Abstract: The oscillation of nonlinear differential equations is used in many applications of mathematical physics, biological and medical physics, engineering, aviation, complex networks, sociophysics and econophysics. The goal of this study is to create some new oscillation criteria for fourth-order differential equations with delay and advanced terms

$$(a_1(x)(w''''(x))^n)' + \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x)w^k(y_j(x)) = 0,$$

and

$$(a_1(x)(w''''(x))^n)' + a_2(x)h(w''''(x)) + \beta(x)f(w(y(x))) = 0.$$

The method is based on the use of the comparison technique and Riccati method to obtain these criteria. These conditions complement and extend some of the results published on this topic. Two examples are provided to prove the efficiency of the main results.

Keywords: Riccati method, advanced term, oscillation, fourth-order, delay differential equations, damped

1 Introduction

Nonlinear differential equations with delay term contribute to some applications in applications of physics, acoustics, biological and medical physics, engineering, aviation, complex networks, sociophysics and econophysics, see refs [1,2].

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Nowadays, the questions regarding the study of oscillation criteria of differential equations have become an important area of research [3,4].

The authors in refs [5–7] discuss some oscillation theories of differential equations of second-order and they used different techniques to obtain the qualitative properties of these equations. In refs [8,9] the authors discussed some oscillation criteria for higher-order differential equations and used comparison techniques with equations of different orders. Agarwal *et al.* [10], Chatzarakis and Li [11], and Bazighifan *et al.* [12] obtained many criteria for oscillation and qualitative properties of differential equations of different orders. Conversely, there has been a great research interest about the study of fractional differential equations and numerical solutions to these equations [13–15] and fractional-ordered differential systems, see refs [16–18].

Park *et al.* [19] establish some qualitative properties of the equation:

$$(a_1(x)(w^{(n-1)}(x))^n)' + \beta(x)w^k(y(x)) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where $k \leq n$ and under condition

$$\int_{x_0}^{\infty} a_1^{-1/n}(s)ds = \infty.$$

In ref. [20], Zhang *et al.* obtained some oscillatory conditions for (1) under

$$\int_{x_0}^{\infty} a_1^{-1/n}(s)ds < \infty. \quad (2)$$

Baculikova *et al.* [21] used the comparison technique to find the parameters of the oscillation of the equation:

$$[a_1(x)(z^{(r-1)}(x))^n]' + \beta(x)f(z(y(x))) = 0.$$

Moreover, Moaaz and Muhib [22,23] presented some oscillation theorems of (1). Also, Zhang *et al.* [24] establish oscillation conditions for (1), where $n = k$.

Zhang *et al.* [25] obtained some oscillatory theorems by the following equation:

$$[a_1(x)(w''''(x))^n]' + \beta(x)f(w(y(x))) = 0,$$

where $n = 4$. Bazighifan [26] obtained some oscillatory conditions by the following equation:

$$[a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n]' + \beta(x)w^k(\gamma(x)) = 0.$$

The authors in ref. [27] use the comparison technique to find oscillation theorems of (4), where $n = k = 1$ and under the condition (6).

Motivated by the results we presented earlier, the oscillation conditions for the following equations are studied:

$$(a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n)' + \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x)w^k(\gamma_j(x)) = 0 \tag{3}$$

and

$$(a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n)' + a_2(x)h(w'''(x)) + \beta(x)f(w(\gamma(x))) = 0. \tag{4}$$

Throughout, the following hypotheses have been assumed:

- (H1) $a_1, a_2, \beta \in C([x_0, \infty), [0, \infty))$, $\gamma_j(x) \in C([x_0, \infty), \mathbb{R})$, n and k are quotient of odd positive integers,
- (H2) $a_1'(x) + a_2(x) \geq 0$, $a_1(x) > 0$, $\beta_j(x) > 0$, $\gamma_j(x) \leq x$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \gamma_j(x) = \infty$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, r$,
- (H3) $h, f \in (\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$, $h(u) \geq b_h u^n > 0$, $f(u) \geq b_f u^n > 0$ for $u \neq 0$ and b_h, b_f are constants. Moreover, equation (3) has been studied under the condition:

$$\int_{x_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a_1^{1/n}(s)} ds = \infty, \tag{5}$$

and equation (4) has been studied under the conditions $\gamma(x) \geq x$ and

$$\int_{x_0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{a_1(s)} \exp \left(- \int_{x_0}^s \frac{a_2(u)}{a_1(u)} du \right) \right]^{1/n} ds < \infty. \tag{6}$$

Definition 1.1. [12] A solution of (3) and (4) is said to be non-oscillatory if it is positive or negative, ultimately; otherwise, it is said to be oscillatory.

Definition 1.2. [12] Equations (3) and (4) are said oscillatory if each of their solutions is oscillatory.

The motivation of studying this article is to obtain new oscillatory properties and to continue the previous works [20,27].

In this article, the Riccati method was used, which depends on reducing the order of the equation. The

comparison technique with a first-order equation has also been relied upon, so these methods give more accurate criteria. These conditions expand and complement some of the previously published results.

2 Oscillation criteria

Here are some lemmas we need to prove the results:

Lemma 2.1. [28] Let $w \in C^m([x_0, \infty), (0, \infty))$ and $w^{(m)}(x)$ is of a fixed sign, on $[x_0, \infty)$ such that, for all $x \geq x_1$,

$$w^{(m-1)}(x)w^{(m)}(x) \leq 0.$$

If we have $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} w(x) \neq 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$, then

$$w(x) \geq \frac{\lambda}{(m-1)!} x^{m-1} |w^{(m-1)}(x)|.$$

Lemma 2.2. [29] If $w^{(r)}(x) > 0$, $r = 0, 1, \dots, r$, and $w^{(r+1)}(x) < 0$, then

$$\frac{w(x)}{x^r/r!} \geq \frac{w'(x)}{x^{r-1}/(r-1)!}.$$

Lemma 2.3. ([3], Lemma 2.2.2) Let $w \in C^m([x_0, \infty), (0, \infty))$ and $w^{(m-1)}(x)w^{(m)}(x) \leq 0$, then

$$w(\theta x) \geq M \theta^{m-1} w^{(m-1)}(x),$$

for $\theta \in (0, 1)$, there exists $M > 0$ and for all sufficient large x .

Lemma 2.4. [30] Let $F > 0$. Then

$$Eu - Fu^{(r+1)/r} \leq \frac{r^r}{(r+1)^{r+1}} E^{r+1} F^{-r}. \tag{7}$$

For convenience, we write the following notations:

$$R(x) := \int_x^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{a_1(x)} \int_x^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) ds \right)^{1/n} dx,$$

$$\bar{R}(x) := \mu_2^{k/n} \int_x^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{a_1(x)} \int_x^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) \left(\frac{\gamma_j(s)}{s} \right)^k ds \right)^{1/n} dx,$$

$$\zeta_{x_0}(x) := \exp \left(\int_{x_0}^x \frac{a_2(x)}{a_1(x)} dx \right)$$

and

$$\widehat{R}(x) := \mu_2^{k/n} \int_x^\infty \left(\frac{1}{a_1(x)\zeta_{x_0}(x)} \int_x^\infty \zeta_{x_0}(x) \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) \left(\frac{y_j(s)}{s} \right)^k ds \right)^{1/n} dx,$$

where $\mu_2 \in (0, 1)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma(x_0, x) &= \exp \left(\int_{x_0}^x \frac{a_2(u)}{a_1(u)} du \right), \\ \delta(x) &= \int_x^\infty \frac{ds}{(a_1(s)\gamma(x_0, s))^{1/n}}, \\ \chi(x) &= \frac{\zeta'(x)}{\zeta(x)} - \frac{b_n a_2(x)}{a_1(x)}, \\ \sigma(x) &= \frac{1}{\gamma^{1/n}(x_0, x)} - \frac{\delta(x)a_2(x)a_1^{1-n/n}(x)}{n} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\tilde{\sigma}(x) = \frac{a_2(x)}{a_1(x)} + \frac{n^{(n+1)}\zeta(x)\sigma^{n+1}(x)\gamma(x_0, x)}{\delta(x)a_1^{1/n}(x)}.$$

Lemma 2.5. *Let w is an eventually positive solution of (3), then $w' > 0$ and $w''' > 0$.*

Theorem 2.6. *If*

$$y'(x) + \frac{\lambda^k \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x) y_j^{3k}(x)}{6^k a_1^{k/n}(y_j(x))} y^{k/n}(y_j(x)) = 0 \quad (8) \quad \text{and}$$

is oscillatory, then (3) is oscillatory.

Proof. Suppose that (3) has a nonoscillatory solution in $[x_0, \infty)$. Then $w(x) > 0$ and $w(y_j(x)) > 0$ for $x \geq x_1$. Let

$$y(x) := a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n > 0 \quad [\text{by Lemma 2.5}].$$

Then from (3), we obtain

$$y'(x) + \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x) w^k(y_j(x)) = 0. \quad (9)$$

$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} w(x) \neq 0$. By Lemma 2.1, we see

$$w^k(y_j(x)) \geq \frac{\lambda^k}{6^k} y_j^{3k}(x) (w'''(y_j(x)))^k, \quad (10)$$

for all $\lambda \in (0, 1)$. By (9) and (10), we see that

$$y'(x) + \frac{\lambda^k}{6^k} \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x) y_j^{3k}(x) (w'''(y_j(x)))^k \leq 0.$$

So, we obtain $y(x) > 0$ and

$$y'(x) + \frac{\lambda^k \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x) y_j^{3k}(x)}{6^k a_1^{k/n}(y_j(x))} y^{k/n}(y_j(x)) \leq 0.$$

From ([31], Theorem 1), equation (8) is nonoscillatory. This is a contradiction. Proof completed. $\square$

Corollary 2.7. *If $n = k$ and*

$$\liminf_{x \rightarrow \infty} \int_{y(x)}^x \frac{\lambda^k \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) y_j^{3k}(s)}{6^k a_1^{k/n}(y_j(s))} ds > \frac{1}{e}, \quad (11)$$

then (3) is oscillatory.

Lemma 2.8. *If*

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{x_0}^\infty \left(M^{k-n} \pi(x) \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x) \frac{y_j^{3n}(x)}{x^{3n}} \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{2^n}{(n+1)^{n+1}} \frac{a_1(x)(\pi'(x))^{n+1}}{\mu^n x^{2n} \pi^n(x)} \right) ds = \infty, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

then $w'' < 0$.

Proof. Let $w''(x) > 0$. From Lemmas 2.1 and 2.2, we find

$$\frac{w(y_j(x))}{w(x)} \geq \frac{y_j^3(x)}{x^3} \quad (13)$$

$$w'(x) \geq \frac{\mu}{2} x^2 w'''(x). \quad (14)$$

Let

$$z_1(x) := \pi(x) \frac{a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n}{w^n(x)} > 0. \quad (15)$$

From (13)–(15), we find

$$\begin{aligned} z_1'(x) & \leq \frac{\pi'(x)}{\pi(x)} z_2(x) - \pi(x) \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x) \frac{y_j^{3n}(x)}{x^{3n}} w^{k-n}(y_j(x)) \\ & \quad - \frac{n\mu}{2} \frac{x^2}{\pi^{1/n}(x) a_1^{1/n}(x)} z_1^{1+1/n}(x). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Since $w'(x) > 0$. From Lemma 2.4 with $E = \pi'/\pi$, $F = n\mu x^2 / (2a_1^{1/n}(x)\pi^{1/n}(x))$, and $u = z_1$, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} z_1'(x) & \leq -M^{k-n} \pi(x) \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x) \frac{y_j^{3n}(x)}{x^{3n}} \\ & \quad + \frac{2^n}{(n+1)^{n+1}} \frac{a_1(x)(\pi'(x))^{n+1}}{\mu^n x^{2n} \pi^n(x)}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies that

$$\int_{x_1}^x \left(M^{k-n} \pi(x) \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x) \frac{y_j^{3n}(x)}{x^{3n}} - \frac{2^n}{(n+1)^{n+1}} \frac{a_1(x)(\pi'(x))^{n+1}}{\mu^n x^{2n} \pi^n(x)} \right) ds \leq z_1(x_1),$$

This is a contradiction (12). Proof completed. □

Theorem 2.9. *If*

$$u''(x) + M^{k-n} \tilde{R}(x)u(x) = 0 \tag{17}$$

is oscillatory, then (3) is oscillatory.

Proof. From Theorem 2.6 and by Lemmas 2.1 and 2.5, we find

$$w'(x) > 0, \quad w''(x) < 0 \text{ and } w'''(x) > 0. \tag{18}$$

Integrating (3), we find

$$\begin{aligned} & a_1(b)(w'''(b))^n \\ &= a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n - \int_x^b \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) w^k(y_j(s)) ds. \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

By Lemma 3 in ref [30] with (18), we obtain

$$\frac{w(y_j(x))}{w(x)} \geq \lambda \frac{y_j(x)}{x},$$

which with (19) gives

$$\begin{aligned} & a_1(b)(w'''(b))^n - a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n \\ &+ \lambda^k \int_x^b \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) \left(\frac{y_j(s)}{s} \right)^k w^k(s) ds \leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

By $w' > 0$, we see

$$\begin{aligned} & a_1(b)(w'''(b))^n - a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n \\ &+ \lambda^k w^k(x) \int_x^b \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) \left(\frac{y_j(s)}{s} \right)^k ds \leq 0. \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Taking $b \rightarrow \infty$, we find

$$-a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n + \lambda^k w^k(x) \int_x^\infty \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) \left(\frac{y_j(s)}{s} \right)^k ds \leq 0,$$

that is,

$$w'''(x) \geq \frac{\lambda^{k/n}}{a_1^{1/n}(x)} w^{k/n}(x) \left(\int_x^\infty \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) \left(\frac{y_j(s)}{s} \right)^k ds \right)^{1/n}.$$

Integrating from x to ∞ , we see

$$-w''(x) \geq \lambda^{k/n} w^{k/n}(x) \int_x^\infty \left(\frac{1}{a_1(x)} \int_x^\infty \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) \left(\frac{y_j(s)}{s} \right)^k ds \right)^{1/n} dx.$$

Hence,

$$w''(x) \leq -\tilde{R}(x)w^{k/n}(x). \tag{21}$$

Let

$$z_2(x) = \frac{w'(x)}{w(x)},$$

then $z_2(x) > 0$ for $x \geq x_1$, and

$$z_2'(x) = \frac{w''(x)}{w(x)} - \left(\frac{w'(x)}{w(x)} \right)^2.$$

From (21), we find

$$z_2'(x) \leq -\tilde{R}(x) \frac{w^{k/n}(x)}{w(x)} - z_2^2(x). \tag{22}$$

Since $w'(x) > 0$. Thus, (22) becomes

$$z_2'(x) + z_2^2(x) + M^{k-n} \tilde{R}(x) \leq 0, \tag{23}$$

From [32], equation (17) is nonoscillatory, and this is a contradiction. Proof completed. □

Theorem 2.10. *Suppose that $k \geq n$ and*

$$\left(\frac{1}{y_j'(x)} u'(x) \right)' + M^{k/n-1} R(x)u(x) = 0 \tag{24}$$

is oscillatory, and then (3) is oscillatory.

Proof. Suppose that (12) and (19) hold. So, we see $y_j'(x) \geq 0$ and $w'(x) \geq 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} & a_1(b)(w'''(b))^n - a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n \\ &+ w^k(y_j(x)) \int_x^b \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(s) ds \leq 0. \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

Thus, (18) becomes

$$w''(x) \leq -R(x)w^{k/n}(y_j(x)). \tag{26}$$

Let

$$z_3(x) = \frac{w'(x)}{w(y_j(x))}, \tag{27}$$

then $z_3(x) > 0$ for $x \geq x_1$, and

$$z_3'(x) = \frac{w''(x)}{w(y_j(x))} - \frac{w'(x)}{w^2(y_j(x))}w'(y_j(x))y_j'(x) \leq \frac{w''(x)}{w(y_j(x))} - y_j'(x)\left(\frac{w'(x)}{w(y_j(x))}\right)^2.$$

From (26) and (27), we find

$$z_3'(x) + M^{k/n-1}R(x) + y_j'(x)z_3^2(x) \leq 0. \tag{28}$$

From [32], (24) is nonoscillatory, and this is a contradiction. This completes the proof. $\square$

Lemma 2.11. ([24], Theorem 2.1) *Suppose that w is an eventually positive solution of (4). Then, there exist two possible cases:*

- (N₁) $w(x) > 0, w'(x) > 0, w'''(x) > 0, w^{(4)}(x) < 0;$
- (N₂) $w(x) > 0, w''(x) > 0, w'''(x) < 0.$

for $x \geq x_1$.

Lemma 2.12. *Let $w(x) > 0$ and (N₁) holds. If*

$$z_4(x) = \zeta(x)\frac{a_1(x)(w''''(x))^n}{w^n(x/2)} > 0, \tag{29}$$

where $\zeta \in C^1([x_0, \infty), (0, \infty))$ and $M > 0$ is a constant, then

$$z_4'(x) \leq -b_f\zeta(x)\beta(x) + \chi(x)z_4(x) - \frac{nMt^2}{2(a_1(x)\zeta(x))^{1/n}}z_4^{\frac{n+1}{n}}(x). \tag{30}$$

Proof. Suppose that $w(x) > 0$ and using Lemma 2.11, we get (N₁) holds. From Lemma 2.3, we see

$$w'(x/2) \geq Mt^2w'''(x). \tag{31}$$

From $z_4(x)$, we obtain

$$z_4'(x) = \zeta'(x)\frac{a_1(x)(w''''(x))^n}{w^n(x/2)} + \zeta(x)\frac{(a_1(w''''(x)))'(x)}{w^n(x/2)} - n\zeta(x)\frac{w'(x/2)a_1(x)(w''''(x))^n}{2w^{n+1}(x/2)}.$$

Using (29) and (31), we find

$$z_4'(x) \leq \frac{\zeta'(x)}{\zeta(x)}z_4(x) + \zeta(x)\frac{(a_1(w''''(x)))'(x)}{w^n(x/2)} - nMt^2\zeta(x)\frac{a_1(x)(w''''(x))^{n+1}(x)}{2w^{n+1}(x/2)}.$$

From (4), we see

$$z_4'(x) \leq \frac{\zeta'(x)}{\zeta(x)}z_4(x) - b_h a_2(x)\frac{z_4(x)}{a_1(x)} - b_f\zeta(x)\beta(x)\frac{w^n(y(x))}{w^n(x/2)} - nMt^2\frac{z_4^{\frac{n+1}{n}}(x)}{2(\zeta(x)a_1(x))^{1/n}} \leq -b_f\zeta(x)\beta(x) + \left(\frac{\zeta'(x)}{\zeta(x)} - b_h\frac{a_2(x)}{a_1(x)}\right)z_4(x) - nMt^2\frac{z_4^{\frac{n+1}{n}}(x)}{2(\zeta(x)a_1(x))^{1/n}}.$$

Hence, we find

$$z_4'(x) \leq -b_f\zeta(x)\beta(x) + \chi(x)z_4(x) - nMt^2\frac{z_4^{\frac{n+1}{n}}(x)}{2(\zeta(x)a_1(x))^{1/n}}.$$

The proof is complete. $\square$

Lemma 2.13. *Let $b_f > 1$ is a constant and (N₂) holds. If*

$$z_5(x) = -\frac{a_1(x)(-w''''(x))^n}{(w''''(x))^n} < 0, \tag{32}$$

then

$$z_5'(x) \leq \frac{b_h a_2(x)}{a_1(x)\delta^n(x)\gamma(x_0, x)} - b_f\beta(x)\left(\frac{\mu}{2}\gamma^2(x)\right)^n - n\frac{z_5^{\frac{n+1}{n}}(x)}{a_1^{\frac{1}{n}}(x)}. \tag{33}$$

Proof. Let that $w(x) > 0$ and (N₂) holds. Since

$$\begin{aligned} &(-a_1(x)(-w''''(x))^n\gamma(x_0, x))' \\ &= (-a_1(x)(-w''''(x))^n)\gamma(x_0, x) + (-a_1(x)(-w''''(x))^n)\gamma(x_0, x)\frac{a_2(x)}{a_1(x)} \\ &= (-1)^{n+1}(-a_2(x)h(w''''(x)) - \beta(x)f(w(y(x))))\gamma(x_0, x) - a_2(x)(-w''''(x))^n\gamma(x_0, x) \\ &\leq (-1)^{n+1}(-b_h a_2(x)(w''''(x))^n - b_f\beta(x)w^n(y(x)))\gamma(x_0, x) - a_2(x)(-w''''(x))^n\gamma(x_0, x) \\ &= (-a_2(x)(-w''''(x))^n(1 - b_h) + b_f\beta(x)(-w^n(y(x))))\gamma(x_0, x) \\ &= (-1)^n(-a_2(x)(w''''(x))^n(1 - b_h) + b_f\beta(x)(w^n(y(x))))\gamma(x_0, x) \\ &\leq -b_f\beta(x)w^n(y(x))\gamma(x_0, x) < 0, \end{aligned}$$

we deduce that $-a_1(x)(-w''''(x))^n\gamma(x_0, x)$ is decreasing. Thus, for $s \geq x \geq x_1$,

$$(a_1(s)\gamma(x_0, s))^{1/n}w''''(s) \leq (a_1(x)\gamma(x_0, x))^{1/n}w''''(x). \tag{34}$$

Dividing both sides of (34) by $(a_1(s)\gamma(x_0, s))^{1/n}$ and integrating from x to b , we get

$$w''(b) \leq w''(x) + (a_1(s)\gamma(x_0, s))^{1/n} w'''(x) \int_x^b \frac{ds}{(a_1(s)\gamma(x_0, s))^{1/n}}.$$

Letting $u \rightarrow \infty$, we arrive that

$$0 \leq w''(x) + (a_1(x)\gamma(x_0, x))^{1/n} w'''(x) \delta(x),$$

which yields

$$-\frac{w'''(x)}{w''(x)} \delta(x) (a_1(x)\gamma(x_0, x))^{1/n} \leq 1.$$

Hence,

$$\frac{a_1(x)(w'''(x))^n}{(w''(x))^n} \geq \frac{-1}{\delta^n(x)\gamma(x_0, x)}.$$

From (32), we find

$$z_5(x) \geq \frac{-1}{\delta^n(x)\gamma(x_0, x)}. \tag{35}$$

and

$$z_5'(x) = \frac{(-a_1(x)(-w'''(x))^n)'}{(w''(x))^n} - n \frac{-a_1(x)(-w'''(x))^{n+1}}{(w''(x))^{n+1}}.$$

From (4) and (32), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} z_5'(x) &= -b_h \frac{a_2(x)}{a_1(x)} z_5(x) - b_f \beta(x) \frac{w^n(\gamma(x))}{(w''(x))^n} - n \frac{z_5^{\frac{n+1}{n}}(x)}{a_1^{\frac{1}{n}}(x)} \\ &= -b_h \frac{a_2(x)}{a_1(x)} z_5(x) - b_f \beta(x) \frac{w^n(\gamma(x))}{(w''(\gamma(x)))^n} \frac{(w''(\gamma(x)))^n}{(w''(x))^n} \\ &\quad - n \frac{z_5^{\frac{n+1}{n}}(x)}{a_1^{\frac{1}{n}}(x)}. \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

By Lemma 2.1, we find

$$w(x) \geq \frac{\mu}{2} x^2 w''(x). \tag{37}$$

Thus, from (35) and (37), we see

$$z_5'(x) \leq \frac{b_h a_2(x)}{a_1(x) \delta^n(x) \gamma(x_0, x)} - b_f \beta(x) \left(\frac{\mu}{2} \gamma^2(x)\right)^n - n \frac{z_5^{\frac{n+1}{n}}(x)}{a_1^{\frac{1}{n}}(x)}.$$

The proof is complete. $\square$

Theorem 2.14. *Let the functions $\zeta, \vartheta \in C^1([x_0, \infty), (0, \infty))$ such that*

$$\limsup_{x \rightarrow \infty} \int_{x_0}^x \left(b_f \zeta(s) \beta(s) - \left(\frac{2}{Ms^2}\right)^n \frac{a_1(s) \zeta(s) (\chi(s))^{n+1}}{(n+1)^{n+1}} \right) ds = \infty. \tag{38}$$

$$\frac{\vartheta(x)}{\delta(x)(a_1(x)\gamma(x_0, x))^{1/n}} + \vartheta'(x) \leq 0 \tag{39}$$

and, for $M > 0$ and $\mu \in (0, 1)$,

$$\limsup_{x \rightarrow \infty} \int_{x_0}^x \left(b_f \beta(s) \left(\frac{\mu \gamma^2(s)}{2} \frac{\vartheta(\gamma(s))}{\vartheta(s)} \delta(s) \right)^n \gamma(x_0, s) - \tilde{\sigma}(s) \right) ds = \infty, \tag{40}$$

then every solution of (4) is oscillatory.

Proof. Proceeding as in the proof of Theorem 2.6.

For case (N_1) . By Lemma 2.12, we find (30) holds. From Lemma 2.4, we set

$$F = \chi(x), \quad E = nMt^2 / (2(a_1(x)\zeta(x))^{1/n}) \text{ and } u = z_4,$$

we have

$$z_4'(x) \leq -b_f \zeta(x) \beta(x) + \left(\frac{2}{Mt^2}\right)^n \frac{a_1(x) \zeta(x) (\chi(x))^{n+1}}{(n+1)^{n+1}}. \tag{41}$$

Integrating from x_1 to x , we obtain

$$\int_{x_1}^x \left(b_f \zeta(s) \beta(s) - \left(\frac{2}{Ms^2}\right)^n \frac{a_1(s) \zeta(s) (\chi(s))^{n+1}}{(n+1)^{n+1}} \right) ds \leq z_4(x_1),$$

which contradicts (38).

For case (N_2) . From the proof of Lemma 2.13, we see

$$\frac{w'''(x)}{w''(x)} \geq \frac{-1}{\delta(x)(a_1(x)\gamma(x_0, x))^{1/n}}.$$

From (39), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{w''(x)}{\vartheta(x)}\right)' &= \frac{w'''(x)\vartheta(x) - w''(x)\vartheta'(x)}{\vartheta^2(x)} \\ &\geq \frac{w''(x)}{\vartheta^2(x)} \left(\frac{\vartheta(x)}{\delta(x)(a_1(x)\gamma(x_0, x))^{1/n}} + \vartheta'(x) \right) \geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

and this means that $w''(x)/\vartheta(x)$ is nondecreasing. So, it follows from $\gamma(x) \geq x$ that

$$\frac{w''(\gamma(x))}{w''(x)} \geq \frac{\vartheta(\gamma(x))}{\vartheta(x)}.$$

Thus, by (36) and (37), we get

$$z_5'(x) \leq \frac{b_h a_2(x)}{a_1(x) \delta^n(x) \gamma(x_0, x)} - b_f \beta(x) \left(\frac{\mu}{2} \gamma^2(x) \right)^n \left(\frac{\vartheta(\gamma(x))}{\vartheta(x)} \right)^n - n \frac{z_5^{\frac{n+1}{n}}(x)}{a_1^{\frac{1}{n}}(x)}. \tag{42}$$

Multiplying (42) by $\delta^n(x) \gamma(x_0, x)$ and integrating from x_1 to x , we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \delta^n(x) \gamma(x_0, x) z_5(x) - \delta^n(x_1) \gamma(x_0, x_1) z_5(x_1) - \int_{x_1}^x \frac{a_2(s)}{a_1(s)} ds \\ & + n \int_{x_1}^x a_1^{-\frac{1}{n}}(s) \delta^{n-1}(s) \gamma(x_0, s) \sigma(s) z_5(s) ds \\ & + \int_{x_1}^x b_f \beta(s) \left(\frac{\mu}{2} \gamma^2(s) \right)^n \left(\frac{\vartheta(\gamma(s))}{\vartheta(s)} \right)^n \delta^n(s) \gamma(x_0, s) ds \\ & + n \int_{x_1}^x \frac{z_5^{\frac{n+1}{n}}(s)}{a_1^{\frac{1}{n}}(s)} \delta^n(s) \gamma(x_0, s) ds \\ & \leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Using Lemma 2.4, we set

$$E = \delta^n(s) \gamma(x_0, s) / a_1^{\frac{1}{n}}(s), \quad F = \int_{x_1}^x a_1^{-\frac{1}{n}}(s) \delta^{n-1}(s) \gamma(x_0, s) \sigma(s),$$

$$u = z_5(x).$$

Thus, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \delta^n(x) \gamma(x_0, x) z_5(x) - \delta^n(x_1) \gamma(x_0, x_1) z_5(x_1) - \int_{x_1}^x \frac{a_2(s)}{a_1(s)} ds \\ & + \int_{x_1}^x b_f \beta(s) \left(\frac{\mu}{2} \gamma^2(s) \right)^n \left(\frac{\vartheta(\gamma(s))}{\vartheta(s)} \right)^n \delta^n(s) \gamma(x_0, s) ds \\ & + \int_{x_1}^x \frac{n^{(n+1)} \zeta(s) \sigma^{n+1}(s) \gamma(x_0, s)}{\delta(s) a_1^{\frac{1}{n}}(x)} ds \\ & \leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by (35), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{x_1}^x \left(b_f \beta(s) \left(\frac{\mu \gamma^2(s)}{2} \frac{\vartheta(\gamma(s))}{\vartheta(s)} \right)^n \delta^n(s) \gamma(x_0, s) - \tilde{\sigma}(s) \right) ds \\ & \leq \delta^n(x) \gamma(x_0, x) z_5(x_1) + 1, \end{aligned}$$

which contradicts (40).

Theorem 2.14 is proved.

Example 2.15. Let the equation:

$$(x^3(w'''(x)))^3)' + \frac{\beta_0}{x^7} w^3(\gamma x) = 0, \tag{43}$$

where $x \geq 1, \gamma \in (0, 1]$ and $\beta_0 > 0$. Let $n = k = 3, \gamma_j(x) = \gamma x, a_1(x) = x^3$, and $\beta(x) = \beta_0/x^7$. So, we obtain

$$\bar{R}(x) = \lambda \left(\frac{\beta_0}{6} \right)^{1/3} \gamma \frac{1}{2x^2}.$$

By Corollary 2.7, we find (43) is oscillatory if

$$\beta_0 > \frac{6^3}{e \left(\ln \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) \gamma^6},$$

$$\beta_0 > \left(\frac{3^4}{2} \right) \frac{1}{\gamma^9},$$

and

$$\beta_0 > 6 \left(\frac{1}{4\gamma} \right)^3.$$

So, equation (43) is oscillatory if

$$\beta_0 > \max \left\{ \left(\frac{3^4}{2} \right) \frac{1}{\gamma^9}, 6 \left(\frac{1}{4\gamma} \right)^3 \right\} = \left(\frac{3^4}{2} \right) \frac{1}{\gamma^9}. \tag{44}$$

Example 2.16. Let the equation

$$(x^2(w'''(x)))' + \frac{x}{2} w'''(x) + \frac{\beta_0}{x^2} w(2x) = 0, \tag{45}$$

where $\beta_0 > 0$ is a constant. Let $n = 1, x_0 = 1, a_1(x) = x^2, a_2(x) = x/2, \beta(x) = x$, and $\gamma(x) = 2x$, we now set $\zeta(x) = x, b_h = b_f = 1$, then

$$\gamma(x_0, x) = \exp \left(\int_{x_0}^x \frac{a_2(u)}{a_1(u)} du \right) = x^{1/2},$$

$$\delta(x) = \int_x^\infty \frac{ds}{(a_1(s) \gamma(x_0, s))^{\frac{1}{n}}} = \frac{2x^{-3/2}}{3}, \quad \vartheta(x) = \frac{2x^{-3/2}}{3},$$

$$\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{\gamma^{\frac{1}{n}}(x_0, x)} - \frac{\delta(x) a_2(x) a_1^{1-n/n}(x)}{n} = \frac{2x^{-1/2}}{3},$$

$$\chi(x) = \frac{-1}{2x},$$

and

$$\tilde{\sigma}(x) = \frac{a_2(x)}{a_1(x)} + \frac{n^{(n+1)} \zeta(x) \sigma^{n+1}(x) \gamma(x_0, x)}{\delta(x) a_1^{\frac{1}{n}}(x)} = \frac{2x^{-1/3}}{3}.$$

Thus, we get

$$\square \quad \limsup_{x \rightarrow \infty} \int_{x_0}^x \left(b_f \zeta(s) \beta(s) - \left(\frac{2}{Ms^2} \right)^n a_1(s) \zeta(s) \chi(s)^{n+1} \right) ds = \infty$$

and

$$\frac{\vartheta(x)}{\delta(x)(a_1(x)\gamma(x_0, x))^{1/n}} + \vartheta'(x) = 0.$$

Also,

$$\limsup_{x \rightarrow \infty} \int_{x_0}^x \left(b_f \beta(s) \left(\frac{\mu \gamma^2(s)}{2} \frac{\vartheta(\gamma(s))}{\vartheta(s)} \delta(s) \right)^n \gamma(x_0, s) - \bar{\sigma}(s) \right) ds = \infty.$$

By Theorem 2.14, we find (45) is oscillatory.

3 Conclusion

In this article, by using the Riccati method and the comparison technique, some new oscillation conditions for fourth-order differential equations are established with delay and advanced terms. Conditions complement and extend some of the results published on this topic. Two examples are discussed to illustrate the efficiency of the main results. Furthermore, nonlinear equations contribute in many applications of mathematical physics, biological and medical physics, engineering, complex networks, aviation, sociophysics and econophysics. The future work is to further study the oscillatory properties of neutral differential equations with p -Laplacian:

$$(a_1(x)(w'''(x))^{p-1})' + \sum_{j=1}^r \beta_j(x) w^{p-1}(\gamma_j(x)) = 0$$

and

$$(a_1(x)(w'''(x))^{p-1})' + a_2(x)h(w'''(x)) + \beta(x)f(w(\gamma(x))) = 0.$$

Under the assumptions:

$$\int_{x_0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a_1^{1/p-1}(s)} ds < \infty$$

and

$$\int_{x_0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{a_1(s)} \exp \left(- \int_{x_0}^s \frac{a_2(u)}{a_1(u)} du \right) \right]^{1/p-1} ds = \infty,$$

where $p > 1$.

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